

EFFECT OF CARBON NANOTUBE DEFORMATION ON ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY OF POLYMER COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Polymer nanocomposites using carbon nanotubes (CNTs) as filler are increasingly viewed as a realistic alternative to conventional smart materials, because they offer higher sensitivity and superior electrical properties [1–4]. Potential applications of carbon nanotube polymer composites as functional materials include electronic devices, photovoltaic cells, highly sensitive strain sensors, and electromagnetic wave interference materials [5, 6]. It is known that the electrical conduction in CNT polymer composites results from the formation of a conductive CNT percolating network between electrodes. There are two types of conduction mechanisms in such a CNT percolating network, namely: (i) the intrinsic conductance of CNTs [7] and (ii) the contact conductance resulting from electron tunneling between sufficiently close nanotubes [8–10]. Various models [11–14] have been developed to predict the electrical conductivity of CNT polymer composites. In most of these models, however, the carbon nanotubes are assumed rigid and the effect of CNT deformation on the intrinsic conductance of CNTs and the electron tunneling at CNT junctions is ignored. Experimental and theoretical works have reported that both the intrinsic resistance of CNTs and the electron tunneling at CNT junctions are dramatically affected by the radial deformation of CNTs [15–17]. For instance, Fuhrer et al. [15] revealed experimentally that the transmission probability between two metallic (5,5) single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs) increased 200 times from 2×10^{-4} to 0.04 by the radial deformation of CNTs with a contact force between the two crossed SWCNTs being estimated only 5 nN [17]. Both experiments and

simulations show that CNTs possess relative low stiffness and strength in the radial direction. Radially compressed, even fully collapsed, CNTs have been observed in CNT polymer composites experimentally [18, 19]. Up to date, the effects of CNTs' radial deformation on the electrical conductivity of CNT polymer composites have rarely been studied.

The objective of this study is to develop a 3-dimensional (3D) CNT percolating network model of relaxed CNTs using Monte Carlo simulations to investigate the electrical properties of CNT polymer composites. The effect of the radial deformation of CNTs is considered when the distance between the walls of two adjacent CNTs is less than the van der Waals distance. The intrinsic electrical conductivity of CNTs is modified in the vicinity of CNT junctions to account for the effect of radial deformation of CNTs, while the contact resistance at CNT junctions is modeled by the Landauer–Büttiker (L-B) formula [20–24]. Validation of the new model is conducted by comparing model predictions with experimental data on the electrical conductivity of multi-walled carbon nanotube (MWCNT) and SWCNT polymer composites in the literature.

2 Formulation of percolation model of relaxed CNTs

2.1 Representative CNT polymer volume cube

Consider a uniformly random distribution of CNTs in a representative CNT polymer volume cube of $L_x \times L_y \times L_z$ as shown in Fig. 1. Each CNT in the model is assumed straight and can be described by a line segment, such that,

$$\begin{aligned}
x_i^1 &= x_i^0 + l_i \sin \alpha_i \cos \beta_i, \\
y_i^1 &= y_i^0 + l_i \sin \alpha_i \sin \beta_i, \\
z_i^1 &= z_i^0 + l_i \cos \alpha_i
\end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where (x_i^0, y_i^0, z_i^0) and (x_i^1, y_i^1, z_i^1) are the coordinates of start and end points of the CNT, l_i is the CNT length, and (α_i, β_i) are the azimuthal and polar angles of the CNT, respectively.

Figure 1. Schematics of randomly distributed CNTs in a representative cube (a). The distance between the walls of two CNTs is more (b) or less (c) than van der Waals distance.

Assume the CNTs are homogeneously distributed in the representative cube. Then, the coordinates of the start point and the azimuthal and polar angles are defined as

$$x_i^0 = L_x \times \text{rand}, \quad y_i^0 = L_y \times \text{rand}, \quad z_i^0 = L_z \times \text{rand} \quad (2a)$$

$$\beta_i = 2\pi \times \text{rand}, \quad \alpha_i = \cos^{-1}(2 \times \text{rand} - 1) \quad (2b)$$

where 'rand' denotes uniformly distributed random numbers in the interval [0, 1]. It is further assumed that the length of each CNT varies and obeys a Weibull distribution $F(x)$ [25], such that,

$$l_i = F^{-1}(\text{rand})$$

$$F(x) \equiv \text{Prob}\{l_i | l_i \leq x\} = 1 - e^{-\left(\frac{x}{a}\right)^b} \quad \text{for } x \geq 0 \quad (3)$$

where a and b are the parameters of Weibull distribution, respectively. Accordingly, the average CNT length is $l_0 = \int_0^\infty x dF(x) = a\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{b} + 1\right)$ and its standard deviation is $S_l = a\sqrt{\Gamma\left(\frac{2}{b} + 1\right) - \Gamma^2\left(\frac{1}{b} + 1\right)}$, where Γ is the gamma function.

It should be noted that the end points of CNTs given in Eq. 1 might be located outside the representative cube. In this case, these CNTs are truncated by the boundary planes and the truncated parts of CNTs are

automatically relocated inside the cube by apply periodic boundary conditions [9].

2.2 Electrical resistance of a relaxed CNT percolating network

The electrical conduction path in the CNT polymer composite is formed by a network of inter-contacted CNTs. There are two types of electrical resistance within the network, i.e., (i) the intrinsic resistance of CNTs and (ii) the contact resistance resulting from electron tunneling at CNT junctions. Many models have been developed in the literature to account for these types of resistance with the rigid CNT assumption [11–14]. From Fig. 1(b)-(c), it is noted that the CNTs generated by Eqs. 1-2 might overlap if one considers the diameter of CNTs. In reality, the contacting CNTs are separated by a so-called van der Waals distance d_{vdW} , see Fig. 1(b), due to the effect of van der Waals force. If the distance between the walls of two CNTs is less than the van der Waals distance due to external loads, the CNTs will deform in the radial direction [15] as shown in Fig. 1(c). Studies have found that the radial deformation of CNTs will affect the CNT's intrinsic and the tunneling resistances at CNT junctions [16]. Accordingly, we will include this effect into the intrinsic and tunneling resistances of a CNT percolating network.

Generally, the intrinsic resistance R_{jk} along one CNT between two nearest contact points j and k with the neighboring CNTs can be evaluated as [9]:

$$R_{jk} = \frac{4l_{jk}}{\pi\sigma_{cnt}D^2} \quad (4)$$

where l_{jk} is the length of the CNT segment between the points j and k , D is the CNT's diameter, σ_{cnt} is the CNT's intrinsic electrical conductivity that is dependent on the diameter and chirality of CNTs, respectively. It should be noted that Eq. 4 is valid for undeformed CNTs and it is modified to account for the effect of CNT's deformation in the following.

Consider a pair deformed CNTs at junction as shown in Fig. 2. Let point m and n be the two ends of the deformation area and l_{mn} the length of the deformed area in the axial direction of a CNT. The deformed length at junction is related to the angle θ between two CNTs. The radial compression can be measured by introducing a parameter

$$\varepsilon = 1 - \frac{D'}{D} \quad (5)$$

where D' is the diameter of the deformed CNT and is defined as

$$D' = \frac{1}{2}(d - d'_{vdw} + D) \quad (6)$$

Here, d is the distance between the axes of two adjacent CNTs and d'_{vdw} is the shortest distance between carbon atoms in the effective contact area of two adjacent CNTs after deformation, respectively. Obviously, there must exist $d'_{vdw} \leq d_{vdw}$.

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of a typical CNT junction.

Thus, the intrinsic conductivity in the deformation area can be expressed in term of the radial deformation of CNTs [26, 27], such that,

$$\sigma_{cnt_d} = \sigma_{cnt} \exp(-\eta\varepsilon) \quad (7)$$

where η is a material constant of CNTs. For instance, $\eta = 32$ for (12, 0) CNTs. Eq. 7 shows that the radial deformation will reduce the CNTs' electrical conductivity exponentially. Correspondingly, the intrinsic resistance of deformed CNTs increases and Eq. 4 is modified as,

$$R_{jk} = \int_0^{l_{jk}} \frac{4}{\pi \sigma_{cnt_d} (D')^2} dl = \frac{4}{\pi \sigma_{cnt} D^2} \int_0^{l_{jk}} \frac{\exp(\eta\varepsilon)}{(1-\varepsilon)^2} dl \quad (8)$$

The unknown parameter D' or d'_{vdw} can be determined by minimizing the potential energy of the CNT junction. Effected by the radial compression of both neighboring CNTs, the total potential energy, E_v of the junction can be expressed by

$$E = 2E_s + E_v \quad (9)$$

where E_s is the radial compressive strain energy of a CNT and E_v is the energy associated with the van der Waals interaction, respectively.

The energy associated with the radial compressive strain of a CNT can be represented by a harmonic potential [28] as

$$E_s = \frac{1}{2} k_s (D - D')^2 \quad (10)$$

where k_s is the equivalent spring constant and can be derived from atomic simulations by keeping one CNT fixed, while slowly moving another CNT towards the fixed CNT in the radial direction. As two CNT are radially compressed, we can calculate the stress-strain curve by coarse-grained molecular dynamics model [28] and derived the spring constant k_s .

The energy associated with the van der Waals interaction is represented by the modified Lennard-Jones potential

$$E_v = \frac{B}{(d'_{vdw})^{12}} - \frac{A}{(d'_{vdw})^6} \quad (11)$$

where the constants $B = 11.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{kJnm}^{12} / \text{mol}$ and $A = 5.96 \times 10^{-3} \text{kJnm}^6 / \text{mol}$ are obtained experimentally. As the distance d between CNTs reducing, the energy associated the van der Waals interaction, E_v , will increase much faster than the strain energy E_s and the shortest distance d'_{vdw} between carbon atoms on the effective contact areas of two CNTs reaches a critical value at near 0.26 nm [16]. Any further decrease in distance d between CNTs will result in flattening the CNTs over a larger deformation area rather than further reducing the shortest distance d'_{vdw} .

The contact resistance is resulted from the electron tunneling at CNT junctions and can be approximated by the L-B formula [8–10, 20–24], such that,

$$R_c = \frac{h}{2e^2} \frac{1}{MT} \quad (12)$$

where M is the total number of conduction channels depending on the type of CNTs, T is the transmission probability, e is the electron charge and h is the Planck's constant, respectively. The transmission probability for electrons to tunnel through the obstacle between CNTs can be estimated by solving the Schrödinger equation with rectangular potential barrier or from the Wentzel-Kramers-Brillouin (WKB) approximation [29, 30], such that,

$$T = \begin{cases} \exp\left(\frac{-d'_{vdw}}{h/\sqrt{8m_e W'_{cnt}}}\right) & 0 < d \leq D + d_{vdw} \\ \exp\left(\frac{-(d-D)}{h/\sqrt{8m_e W_{cnt}}}\right) & D + d_{vdw} < d \leq D + 2d_{vdw} \\ \exp\left(\frac{-(d-D-2d_{vdw})}{h/\sqrt{8m_e (W_{cnt} - W_{poly})}} + \frac{-2d_{vdw}}{h/\sqrt{8m_e W_{cnt}}}\right) & D + 2d_{vdw} < d \leq d_{cutoff} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

where m_e is the electron mass, W_{cnt} and W'_{cnt} are the work functions of CNTs before and after deformation, W_{poly} is the work function of CNT and polymer matrix, respectively. The work function of deformed CNTs is the function of CNT's deformation and can be approximated by curve fitting of the calculated values [31, 32], such that,

$$W'_{cnt} = W_{cnt} + \gamma(1 - D'/D) = W_{cnt} + \gamma\varepsilon \quad (14)$$

where γ is the rate of work function and the deformed diameter of CNTs can be determined by minimizing the potential energy at the CNT junctions. Obviously, the contact resistance decreases as CNTs are compressed at the junction.

Once the percolating resistor network is identified with all types of resistances in the resistor network and all variables associated with the radial deformation are evaluated, the Dulmage Mendelsohn decomposition method [33] is applied to eliminate those resistors that do not participate in conducting the current flow. The total resistivity of the percolating CNT network can be obtained from the positive semi-definite matrix equations representing Kirchhoff's circuit laws [34–37]. A Cholesky decomposition algorithm for sparse matrices [37, 38] is employed to solve these equations.

3 Results and discussions

In the following analyses, the van der Waals separation distance d_{vdw} is defined as 0.34 nm per Ref. [39]. Several experiments reported that the intrinsic conductivity of CNTs, σ_{cnt} , ranges from 5×10^3 to 5×10^6 S/m for MWCNTs and from 17 to 2×10^7 S/m for SWCNTs [9]. It should be noted that the electrical properties for an individual CNT are dependent on its diameter and chirality. In polymer matrix composites, electrons scattering from the

polymer molecular chains impact the intrinsic conductivities of these CNTs. The molecular chains are dependent on the type of polymer considered and its fabrication process [40]. For metallic SWCNTs, the energy band is expected to be doubly degenerated with a channel number $M = 2$ [22]. However, MWCNTs possess a much larger multichannel number M ranging from 460 to 490 [41]. The cutoff distance for the van der Waals effect d_{cutoff} is chosen to be 1.4 nm [9], which is larger than the distance where the transmission probability is less than 10^{-6} . In this case, the tunneling effects can be ignored. The work functions of various CNTs were found to vary from 4.5 to 6 eV, while typical values for nylon 66, polystyrene, polycarbonate, and polyimide are 3.95 eV, 4.22 eV, 4.26 eV, and 4.36 eV, respectively [42].

To compare our simulation results with the experimental values of MWCNT and SWCNT polymer composites, the following parameters were selected in our calculations. The parameters for work functions were $W_{cnt} = 4.7$ eV, $W_{poly} = 4$ eV, $\gamma = -7.5$. The parameters in the Weibull distribution for CNT length were set to $a = 5.6403 \mu\text{m}$ and $b = 2.4$. The size of representative cube was selected as $5.5 \mu\text{m} \times 5.5 \mu\text{m} \times 5.5 \mu\text{m}$ [9]. For MWCNT polymer composites, the diameter of CNTs is $D = 50$ nm, the number of conduction channels is $M = 460$, $\eta = 5$ and the average CNT length $l = 5 \mu\text{m}$, respectively. In addition, the value of the intrinsic MWCNT conductivity was chosen to be $\sigma_{cnt} = 1 \times 10^4$ S/m [9, 11]. For SWCNT polymer composites, the corresponding parameters were set to $D = 6.9$ nm, $M = 2$, $\eta = 15$, $l = 0.31 \mu\text{m}$; and the value of the intrinsic SWCNT conductivity was chosen to be $\sigma_{cnt} = 1 \times 10^4$ S/m.

3.1 Variation of Resistance vs. radial deformation of CNTs

To understand the variation of resistance caused by the radial deformation of CNTs at junction quantitatively, Fig. 3 shows the intrinsic and contact resistance at a CNT junction with various distances between the axes of two neighboring CNTs. The length of the CNTs in the vicinity of junction is assumed 10 times of the diameter of CNT in the calculation, while the angle between two CNTs is set to be 90° . When d is greater than $D + d_{vdw}$, the CNT does not deform and the value of the intrinsic

resistance is a constant. On the contrary, the intrinsic resistances of CNTs increase as d increases. When d is less than $D + d_{vdw}$ and the CNT starts to deform in the radial direction, the electron scattering enhances significantly and the intrinsic resistance increases quickly due to the lattice distortion in the deformation area. Unlike the intrinsic resistance, the contact resistance at CNT junctions reduces with the decreasing distance between CNTs. This is because the electron transmission probability increases as the height and width of potential barrier reduced by the radial deformation. As shown in Fig. 3, the contact resistance is less sensitive than the intrinsic resistance to the distance between the deformed CNTs. The reduction in contact resistance caused by the radial deformation is relatively smaller than the increase in the intrinsic resistance of the same junction. This leads to the increase of total resistance at the junction as the radial deformation develops, which is consistent with the experimental observations [16].

Figure 3. Calculated contact resistance and intrinsic resistance at the junctions of (a) SWCNT polymer composite and (b) MWCNT polymer composite vs. distance between the axes of two neighboring CNTs.

3.2 Percentage of deformed CNT junctions in percolating CNT network

To further understand the impact of the radial deformation of CNTs on the resulting resistance of percolating CNT network, we have calculated the percentage of CNT junctions formed by deformed CNTs in the percolating network. Fig. 4 shows the statistics of total CNT junctions and the junctions of deformed CNTs in the entire CNT network vs. the volume fraction of CNTs. The solid points represent the total numbers of CNT junctions while the hollow points represent the numbers of junctions formed by the radially deformed CNTs only. Two cases are considered: (i) MWCNTs with a diameter of $D = 50$ nm and (ii) SWCNTs with a diameter of $D = 6.9$ nm. It can be seen clearly that the majority of CNT junctions are formed by the radially deformed CNTs, e.g., 83% for the MWCNTs and 62% for SWCNTs, respectively. The larger the CNT diameter, the higher the percentage of deformed CNT junctions. The statistics explains the overall electrical conductivity of CNT polymer composites is reduced after considering the effect of radial deformation of CNTs. In addition, it also shows the necessity to include the effect of CNT deformation in estimating the electrical conductivity of CNT polymer composites. Furthermore, we also find that a percolating CNT network is easier to form with larger diameter of CNTs for a given volume fraction. For instance, the diameter of SWCNTs is much smaller than MWCNTs. Thus, the percolation threshold of MWCNT polymer composites is much lower than SWCNT polymer composites.

Figure 4. Effect of volume fraction and diameter of CNTs on numbers of junction where electron can tunnel through between neighboring CNTs.

3.3 Total resistance of junctions vs. angle between two radially deformed CNTs

In addition to the severity of radial deformation, the total resistance of junctions can be affected by the angle between two deformed CNTs too. As shown in Fig. 5, the effect of the angle θ on the total resistance of junctions is presented. For the purposes of comparison, the severity of deformation is assumed to be $\varepsilon = 0.1$ and the length of CNTs at the junction is set to be 10 times of the diameter in both cases of MWCNTs and SWCNTs. It can be seen that the resistance reaches the minimum values at the angle $\theta = 90^\circ$ and the maximum values at the angles $\theta = 0^\circ$ and $\theta = 180^\circ$. As the angle changes from 90° to 180° , the deformation area increases and so does the intrinsic resistances of CNTs in this larger area. Furthermore, it shows that the total resistance in the vicinity of junctions formed by SWCNTs is about 100 times greater than that formed by MWCNTs. This angle effect is so significant and should not be ignored.

Figure 5. Total resistance of junctions vs. angle between two radial deformed CNTs.

3.4 Validation and comparison with experiments

Finally, we validated our new CNT percolating network model with experimental results. Fig. 6 shows the comparisons of simulation results and experimental data of electrical conductivities of MWCNT and SWCNT polymer composites. The dotted and solid lines represent the simulation results without and with considering the radial deformation of CNTs, respectively. Compared with the experimental data, the predictions of present model show a better agreement with the experimental data in both MWCNT [11, 43, 44] and SWCNT [45–47]

polymer composites than the existing models [9] that neglected the effect of the radial deformation of CNTs. In both MWCNT and SWCNT cases, it is found that the effect of the radial deformation of CNTs results in a lower electrical conductivity of CNT polymer composites as discussed before. Accordingly, the percolation threshold of both MWCNT and SWCNT polymer composites is increased if the effect of radial deformation of CNTs is considered. Finally, it can be seen that the CNT deformation plays a more dominant role in SWCNT polymer composites than MWCNT polymer composites.

Figure 6. Comparisons of electrical conductivity of (a) MWCNT and (b) SWCNT polymer composites.

4. Conclusions

The present work studied the impact of the radial deformation of CNTs on the electrical conductivity of CNT polymer composites. A new model has been developed to account for the radial deformation in both the intrinsic and contact resistance of CNTs. The electrical properties of bulk CNT polymer

composites with different volume fraction of CNTs are analyzed by the Monte Carlo simulations. The analyses show the new model agrees with the experimental data better than the existing models that neglected the deformation effect. The analyses find that: The effect of the radial deformation of CNTs on the resulting electrical conductivity of CNT polymer composites is significant and cannot be neglected. The intrinsic resistance of CNTs in the vicinity of CNT junction increases while the contact resistance decreases as the CNT being radially compressed. The increasing rate of the intrinsic resistance exceeds the decreasing rate of the contact resistance, leading to a net increase of resistance in the percolating CNT network; The total resistances of junctions vary significantly with the angles between two adjacent CNTs and this effect cannot be neglected.

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